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Cultural journey throughout the island of Cuba

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ABSTRACT

This paper is a photographic summary of a cultural expedition conducted in November 2012 on the island of Cuba. The purpose was to explore and capture a glimpse of the natural and cultural beauty of this incredible country, renowned for its strong tourism potential and spirit of freedom. Cuba is one of the most beautiful countries we have encountered, with some of the most welcoming people, a rich history of resistance to colonialism, delicious traditional cuisine, and exceptional safety for travelers, as violence is virtually nonexistent. The photographs highlight colonial buildings and other architectural styles, churches, museums, natural landscapes, elements of the fauna and flora, and, of course, the Cuban people.

Keywords: Cuba, tourism, culture, history

INTRODUCTION

The first time I visited Cuba was in July 1990, when I participated in the Latin American Botany Congress. I was captivated by the architectural beauty of the capital, Havana, and especially by the kindness and rich culture of the Cuban people. Twenty-two years after this memorable experience, my wife and I embarked on a journey around the island of Cuba, from November 1 to 23, 2012, aiming to explore as many historical cities as possible, as well as its diverse natural environments, gaining a deeper appreciation of its fauna and flora.

The photographs presented in this report were taken by Fabio Rossano Dario and Cristina De Vincenzo, using a cell phone and a digital camera. Photo 66 was taken by the Cuban photographer Alberto "Korda" Gutiérrez. Photos 66, 137, and 138 were taken by unknown authors and are now in the public domain.

The Republic of Cuba is an archipelago located in the Caribbean Sea, at the entrance to the Gulf of Mexico, between Florida and the Yucatán Peninsula. It consists of the Island of Cuba, the Isle of Juventud, and more than four thousand small islands and cays (**Figure 1**). Cays are small, shallow, sandy islands formed on the surface of coral reefs, typically covered with mangrove vegetation and surrounded by shallow beaches [1]. The Island of Cuba has an area approximately three times smaller than that of Poland. The capital, Havana, is home to just over two million people, accounting for around 20% of the country's total population.

We arrived in Cuba via José Martí International Airport in Havana. José Martí, born in Havana on January 28, 1853, was a Cuban nationalist politician, intellectual, journalist, translator, teacher, philosopher, and poet. He is considered a Cuban national hero for his pivotal role in the liberation of the country from Spanish rule. Known as the "Apostle of Cuban Independence" [2], Martí died fighting against invading Spanish troops while defending Cuba's independence. His political ideas laid the foundation for anti-imperialist movements across Latin America. Martí's ideals, together with Marxism-Leninism, continue to influence Cuban politics to this day [3, 4].

The old city of Havana and its fortifications were added to UNESCO's World Heritage List in 1982. Havana is one of the most beautiful cities in the world, boasting a rich historical and cultural tradition, characterized by its eclectic and monumental nature. At one time, Havana was the most fortified city on the American continent, with military fortifications such as the

Fortaleza de San Carlos de la Cabaña and the Castillo de los Tres Santos Reyes del Morro serving as outstanding examples of 16th-century architecture (**Photo 1**). A cannon is fired nightly at exactly 9:00 PM in a tradition known as "El Cañonazo de las 9." This practice, a remnant from colonial times, once signaled the closing of the city gates.

Figure 1. Cuban Map (<https://yandex.com>).

You can reach Castillo del Morro via the Malecón, walking along the seafront from the Vedado neighborhood to Old Havana (Habana Vieja). The Malecón is a broad esplanade, roadway, and seawall that extends 8 km along Havana's coastline. It is a beloved spot for Cubans and a popular gathering place (**Photo 2**).

Havana's architecture is eclectic, featuring many buildings in the Baroque style from the period when Cuba was a Spanish colony. The city's cathedral (**Photo 3**), the Palacio del Marqués de Arcos (**Photo 4**), and the Palacio de los Capitanes Generales (**Photo 5**), built in the mid-18th century, are prime examples of Cuban Baroque architecture. Neoclassical influences can be seen in almost all newer buildings in Havana, particularly in those constructed at the end of the 19th century in the El Vedado neighborhood.

In the early 20th century, Havana embraced styles such as Art Nouveau, Art Deco, and Eclecticism (**Photos 6–10**). Modernist architectural features began to appear in the 1950s, seen in structures like the Habana Libre Hotel (formerly the Habana Hilton) (**Photo 11**) and Edificio Focsa, a 39-story complex built in 1956. Inspired by Le Corbusier's concept of an autonomous "city within a city," the Edificio Focsa includes 400 apartments, garages, a school, a supermarket, and restaurants on its top floor (**Photo 12**).

The National Capitol Building in Havana, built in 1929 in a blend of Neoclassical and Art Nouveau architectural styles, served as the seat of the Cuban government until the Cuban Revolution in 1959. It now houses the Cuban Academy of Sciences. Its design resembles the

United States Capitol in Washington, D.C., but its dome is inspired by that of the Pantheon in Paris (**Photo 13**).

The Gran Teatro de La Habana Alicia Alonso (**Photo 14**) is one of Havana's premier cultural institutions and serves as the home of the Cuban National Ballet. It is also one of the city's most iconic architectural landmarks. Built in the Art Nouveau style, the theater opened in 1915. Alicia Alonso (1920–2019), after whom the theater is named, was a celebrated Cuban dancer and choreographer, regarded as one of the most influential artists of the 20th century and the last diva of classical ballet.

Cuba is a country with unparalleled cultural richness, offering a wide range of musical performances, theater, ballet, and cinema not only in Havana but also in cities throughout the island. The Cuban people experience art around the clock. We had the honor of attending a performance by the Cámara de Camagüey Orchestra at Iglesia San Francisco de Paula, featuring violinist Evelio Tiele. The concert included works by Mozart, Mendelssohn, and Benjamin Britten. Evelio Tiele studied violin in Paris with Jacques Thibaud (1880–1953) and René Benedetti (1901–1975), and at the Tchaikovsky Conservatory in Moscow, where he was a student of renowned violinists David Oistrakh (1908–1974) and Igor Oistrakh (1931–2021).

Walking through Old Havana is like stepping back in time, especially when we find ourselves on deserted streets lined with houses in precarious condition, alongside classic cars that continue to circulate in perfect condition. These cars have been a part of the city since the Cuban Revolution in 1959, when the United States—supporting the corrupt and repressive regime of dictator Fulgencio Batista (1901–1973)—imposed an economic embargo on Cuba, a policy that persists to this day (**Photos 15–20**).

From the moment of the Cuban Revolution's victory, led by Cuban lawyer Fidel Castro (1926–2016) and Argentine doctor Ernesto "Che" Guevara (1928–1967), the United States imposed several economic sanctions on Cuba. Many documents, weapons, and vehicles from the history of the Cuban Revolution can be seen at the Museum of the Revolution in Havana (**Photos 21–28**). We spent an entire morning in this fascinating museum, learning about Cuba's history, which helped us better understand the significance of both the War of Independence and the Cuban Revolution, as well as the tense relations with the neighboring United States.

The ambitions of the United States, according to a statement by the Spanish ambassador to Florida, Luis de Onís (1762–1827), in 1812, were to establish its borders, including the annexation of Cuba, and they would do everything to achieve this. In the words of U.S. President James Monroe (1758–1831): "America is for the Americans." The expansionist and interventionist actions of the United States, known as the Monroe Doctrine, were thus declared [5].

Cuba would become the main target of the United States, since, according to Monroe: "Domination of this island and Florida would give the United States control of the Gulf of Mexico and the countries of the isthmus." Florida was invaded in 1818, but the acquisition of the island of Cuba, which Thomas Jefferson (1743–1826) had attempted to buy from Spain in 1803, proved to be more difficult [6]. Numerous efforts were made to conquer Cuba, including invasions, bombings, ecological crimes, murders, assassination attempts, economic blockades, and various types of sabotage, such as the introduction of viruses and harmful bacteria to affect the civilian population, agriculture, and livestock in Cuba. The damage was often irreparable, but Cuba resisted.

The Spanish-American War, fought between 1898 and 1902, provided a prime opportunity for U.S. troops to invade Cuba under the guise of "supporting" the Caribbean

country's independence. The accidental explosion of the U.S. battleship *Maine* in Havana served as the pretext President William McKinley (1843–1901) needed to accuse Spain and enter the war. The Spanish fleet was annihilated in Santiago de Cuba, and the U.S. Marines finally landed on the coveted island. In return for their "support" of the Cuban revolutionaries, the U.S. imposed a military government on Cuba during the first four years of its independence [7]. This government was led by General Leonard Wood (1860–1927), who established a military base in Guantánamo—later used as a U.S. detention camp where political suspects from around the world continue to be imprisoned and tortured to this day.

The Platt Amendment, approved by the U.S. Senate on March 2, 1901, and shamefully incorporated into the Cuban Constitution, ensured U.S. occupation of Cuba and imposed economic and military control over the country, among other humiliating conditions that violated Cuban sovereignty and independence. Article 1 of this disgraceful amendment stated that "the Government of Cuba would not sign any agreement that would allow a foreign power to obtain, for naval or military purposes, a part of the island." In Article 3, "the Government of Cuba accepted that the United States could exercise the right to intervene to preserve Cuban independence and maintain a government capable of protecting life and property." Article 6 "gave the United States the right to establish military bases on Cuban territory" [8].

General Leonard Wood described the Platt Amendment as follows: "With the control we have over Cuba, which will no doubt soon become a possession, we will soon control the entire sugar trade in the world. I believe that the acquisition of Cuba is highly desirable for the United States. The island will gradually become Americanized, and in due time, we will have one of the richest and most coveted possessions on the planet."

Based on the Platt Amendment, U.S. Marines would land in Cuba multiple times, including during the democratic elections of 1906. The military intervention, led by General Charles Magoon (1861–1920), lasted three long years, until 1909 [9]. In 1912, Cuba experienced another military intervention, this time aimed at protecting U.S. interests in Havana, particularly the efficient network of corruption.

If it weren't for the Cuban Revolution, led by Fidel Castro, which overthrew the dictatorship of Fulgencio Batista (supported by the U.S.), the United States would have maintained control over Cuba. The Revolution received support from the Soviet Union and intellectuals from around the world, and it initiated a process of agrarian and urban reform, an efficient healthcare program, mass literacy, and the nationalization of the Cuban economy, along with the creation of new job opportunities. Much of what had been taken by U.S. capitalists was returned to the Cuban people.

Between 1959 and 1960, hundreds of bombings were carried out over Cuba in an attempt to destabilize the new revolutionary government. On April 17, 1961, President John F. Kennedy (1917–1963) supported the invasion of Cuba, with the landing of anti-Castro Cuban exiles, known as the "gusanos" (worms), who came from Florida directly to Playa Girón. However, the invasion, orchestrated by the CIA (Central Intelligence Agency), failed.

Other interventions by the United States in Cuba further worsened the island's economic situation, such as the Torricelli Law, enacted in 1992 during the presidency of George H. W. Bush (1924–2018). This law, which remains in effect today, imposes harsh economic sanctions on countries that maintain any type of relationship with Cuba. According to the law, it is prohibited for any vessel, regardless of its nationality or flag, to dock in U.S. ports if it has docked in a Cuban port within the last six months. Condemned by the United Nations, the Torricelli Law violates fundamental principles of freedom of trade and navigation under

International Law, and aims to discourage commercial relations between other countries and Cuba. The law also abruptly halted trade in medicines and food that Cuba had maintained with subsidiaries of U.S. companies based outside U.S. territory [10].

In addition to the economic, commercial, and financial blockade against the island, the U.S. carried out several acts of terrorism and biological weapon attacks against Cuba. The most horrifying aspect of this campaign of terrorism was the introduction of dengue hemorrhagic fever during the presidency of Ronald Reagan (1911–2004). Between June 1 and October 10, 1981, more than 300,000 cases of dengue were reported in Cuba, of which more than 30,000 were hemorrhagic. In the first week of the outbreak, 158 people died, most of them children. The United States, in addition to producing the virus and introducing it to the Cuban population, refused to sell the chemical product needed to eliminate the transmitting agent, the *Aedes aegypti* mosquito. However, the product was purchased from Japan.

Still dissatisfied with its failure to collapse Cuba's economic and political system, the Helms-Burton Act was passed in 1996 during the presidency of Bill Clinton [11]. This law codified all blockade prohibitions and sought to prevent foreign investment in Cuba, while also institutionalizing subversion financed and directed by the U.S. government as a means of breaking the spirit of independence of the Cuban people. In accordance with paragraph (c) of Article II of the Geneva Convention for the Prevention and Punishment of the Crime of Genocide (December 9, 1948), the blockade imposed on Cuba by the United States government constitutes an act of genocide and, therefore, a crime under International Law.

Against the more than 200 years of attempts at annexing Cuba by the United States, the words of Cuban intellectual José Martí, spoken on March 21, 1889, remain valid: “No worthy Cuban can want to see his country annexed by another. Those who fought in the war, those who were exiled, those who build a homeland with their sweat—the engineers, the teachers, the journalists, the lawyers, and the poets—do not want the annexation of Cuba by the United States and are suspicious of the disastrous elements that, like worms in the blood, began their work of destruction”.

The Cuban people are incredibly creative, and in order to circumvent economic sanctions, as well as to support an economy focused on tourism, there are family-owned restaurants known as the famous "paladares" (the name and the ingenious concept for these restaurants stem from a Brazilian soap opera). In paladares, tourists can enjoy delicious homemade Cuban food (**Photo 29**). Tricycles with a double seat behind the cyclist travel around Habana Vieja, taking tourists to various points of interest (**Photo 30**). There are also "cocotaxis", which are motorized tricycles resembling scooters with a double or triple seat behind the driver, covered by a spherical structure open at the front. The name "cocotaxi" comes from the word "coco," meaning coconut. The vehicle's body is typically yellow and round, resembling a half-coconut (**Photos 31, 32**).

Cuba is famous for the high quality of its tobacco, recognized as the best in the world, and a visit to a cigar factory is a must to see both the museum and the cigar manufacturing process. We recommend Real Fabrica de Tabacos Partagás, located in the center of Havana (**Photo 33**). The factory was founded in 1845 by the Spanish entrepreneur Jaime Partagás, and around 500 people work there, selecting leaves and rolling cigars by hand, producing famous brands such as Montecristo and Cohíba.

A walk along Calle Obispo is a must. It is the busiest street in Habana Vieja, where you can admire the finest examples of Cuba's colonial and eclectic Art Nouveau architecture (**Photo 34**). There are some traditional places to enjoy a daiquiri, such as El Floridita, which is very

popular due to its fame and the quality of its cuisine. If tourists are looking for a quieter spot, one option is the bar at Hotel Ambos Mundos (**Photo 35**). The writer Ernest Hemingway (1899-1961) was a regular at El Floridita, but he lived at the Hotel Ambos Mundos between 1932 and 1939, in room 511, where he wrote his famous novel *For Whom the Bell Tolls*. We drank daiquiris at both places, and they were delicious. The daiquiri is Cuba's traditional drink, and the El Floridita bar is considered "the birthplace of the daiquiri," which is made with rum, sugar, lemon, and a light touch of Maraschino liqueur, all blended with plenty of ice to give the drink a frappe-like consistency.

There are many museums in Havana. The Mural Painting Museum (Museo de los Murales) is located in a historic building, considered the oldest house in Havana, on Calle Obispo (**Photo 36**). This museum showcases various pictorial treasures found on the walls and facades of buildings in Habana Vieja, representing the city's different artistic periods.

After the economic embargo against Cuba, Fidel Castro decided to make the country self-sufficient in milk and create the best ice cream in the world. He oversaw the construction of the largest ice cream shop in the world, which began in 1966, a project led by Célia Sánchez (1920-1980), an important figure in the Cuban Revolution. The ice cream shop was named Coppelia (**Photos 37, 38**) and was designed by architect Mario Girona (1924-2008) to accommodate a thousand people at once, with a hall and ice cream factory. Coppelia is a global reference in ice cream production. One of the scenes in the film *Fresa y Chocolate (Strawberry and Chocolate)*, directed by Tomás Gutiérrez Alea, takes place in the Coppelia ice cream shop. The Cuban film won the Goya Award for Best Ibero-American Film in 1994.

Casa de las Américas is an organization founded in Cuba in 1959 to promote the exchange of Cuban culture with that of other Latin American countries. It was established a few months after the victory of the Cuban Revolution, by the revolutionary Haydée Santamaría (1922-1980), who presided over the entity until 1980. The organization occupies an Art Deco-style building (**Photo 39**), and in this cultural space, there are festivals, exhibitions, literary meetings, theater, visual arts, and music events. The Casa de las Américas Literary Prize has had judges such as Júlio Cortázar, Italo Calvino, José Lezama Lima, Ernesto Cardenal, Carlos Fuentes, Allen Ginsberg, André Gorz, Eduardo Galeano, and José Saramago.

La Plaza de la Revolución (**Photo 40**) is one of the largest squares in the world, covering 72,000 square meters. It holds great historical value, as it has been the site of several key acts and events of the Cuban Revolution. A million people gathered there to listen to Fidel Castro's long speeches. In the center of the square stands the José Martí Memorial, a 142-meter-high monument, the tallest structure in all of Havana, which houses a museum and a viewpoint. In front of the monument is a 17-meter-high marble statue of José Martí, seated and pensive (**Photos 41, 42**).

It takes about two hours by car or bus to reach Varadero, located on the Matanzas Peninsula. This beach city, known for its crystal-clear turquoise waters, is one of the most popular destinations in the Caribbean. Varadero is well-developed for tourism, with a large complex of all-inclusive hotels and spas (**Photos 43, 44**).

Starting from Havana, it takes about two hours by taxi or on a bus excursion, which can be booked through travel agencies located in the city's main hotels, to reach Viñales Valley, an incredible geological formation in the Sierra de los Órganos in the province of Pinar del Río. The valley features a set of isolated residual hills with steep, sandy sides, composed of limestone, marble, or dolomite, and surrounded by alluvial plains. These geological formations are called mogotes (**Photos 45, 46**). The climate around the mogotes is cooler and more humid

than in most parts of Cuba, and the fertility of the land, along with the life sustained by the transported and deposited minerals, makes the area unique [12]. The mogotes are one of the reasons why Viñales Valley was declared a World Heritage Site by UNESCO.

The Pinar del Río region is exclusively dedicated to tobacco production. In the rural areas, we encounter guajiros, rural workers (**Photos 47, 48**). When the Spanish arrived on the Island of Cuba in 1492, the invaders were fascinated by the indigenous people, who always carried bundles of "weeds" to absorb the fragrant smoke. Soon after, the Spanish colonists began cultivating and smoking tobacco, and those "weeds" became a profitable crop. Tobacco cultivation, from planting to preparing tobacco leaves for making Cuban cigars, involves a set of artisanal techniques that have been rigorously passed down from generation to generation. The leaves are harvested manually and hung on clotheslines inside sheds, which are typically made of wood and covered with straw. These sheds have openings to regulate temperature and humidity. Over the course of several weeks, the leaves dehydrate and transform from green to brown [13].

In the Viñales Valley, 4 km from the city of Viñales, there is the Mural de la Prehistoria (Mural of Prehistory), painted on the natural wall of a mogote. The work began in 1961, as a project by muralist Leovigildo González Morillo, a disciple of the Mexican Marxist muralist Diego Rivera (1886-1957) [14]. The mural is 120 meters long and is considered one of the largest outdoor paintings in the world. It took four years to complete and had the support of twenty peasants. The objective is to represent the evolutionary process of life from the artist's perspective. It is filled with bright colors and depicts fauna, including dinosaurs, snails, giant marine reptiles, and human beings (**Photos 49, 50**). Another tourist attraction we visited in the Pinar del Río region was the Cueva del Indio. It's a cave that can be traversed by boat along the San Vicente River, surrounded by stalactites and stalagmites.

Continuing by car towards Cienfuegos, we cross a large area of sugarcane plantations (*Saccharum officinarum*) (**Photo 51**). Sugar production has historically been the most important economic activity on the Island. Cuba was once the largest sugar producer in the world. After the Cuban Revolution in 1959, sugar mills were nationalized, with the Soviet Union as its largest partner, sending fuel and machinery to Cuba, as the United States had imposed a comprehensive trade embargo on the Island in 1962, which continues to this day. With the collapse of the Soviet Union in 1991, Cuban sugar production was reduced by half, causing serious damage to the Island's economy. Subsequently, Cuba turned to tourism and the restructuring of the sugar industry [15].

Cienfuegos is located in the southern center of the island, on the bay of the same name. It is one of Cuba's main ports and an important commercial center for sugarcane plantations. Declared a World Heritage Site by UNESCO in 2005, Cienfuegos is a city open to the sea, with an incredible maritime atmosphere. It is the city of the famous singer Benny Moré (1919-1963). Known as the "Pearl of the South of Cuba," the city preserves one of the most homogeneous urban centers on the island in terms of architecture, with classic facades and columns reminiscent of France in the 19th century. This style was inspired by its founder, the Frenchman Louis de Clouet de Pietre (1766-1848), who established the city in 1819. Among the main attractions is the Tomás Terry Theatre, declared a national monument. It is considered one of the most elegant eclectic buildings in the city, with a capacity for 950 people, decorated with Carrara marble, hand-carved wooden floors, and classicist-style frescoes on the ceiling. We also visited the Palacio de Valle, an architectural marvel that was once an important casino.

This two-story building is richly decorated with Gothic, Venetian, and Neo-Moorish motifs, similar in style to the Alcázar of Granada and Seville (**Photos 52-60**).

From Cienfuegos to Santa Clara, we saw many billboards along the road highlighting the achievements of the Cuban Revolution, such as the eradication of illiteracy, public health as a human right for all citizens, the best preventive health system in the world, the best medical school in the world, the safest country for tourism, all children in school, and no people sleeping on the streets. We also saw many billboards featuring the image of Che Guevara, thanking the Argentine doctor for his significant involvement in the Cuban Revolution (July 26, 1953, to January 1, 1959), and especially for liberating the city of Santa Clara, which marked the victory of the guerrillas (**Photos 61-62**).

Santa Clara is known as “the city of heroic guerrilla warfare”, because in this city, in 1958, the last battle took place, led by Che Guevara, which marked the end of the dictatorship in Cuba. We visited the Che Guevara Memorial in Plaza de la Revolución, built in 1987. The memorial is massive, and at the entrance, there is a large bronze statue of Che with a plastered arm, which was fractured in a battle prior to Santa Clara, surrounded by many imperial palm trees. Bas-reliefs carved in the marble of the memorial depict scenes from the battles and Che's famous farewell letter to Fidel, before he left for Bolivia.

The memorial is divided into two parts: the museum and the mausoleum. The museum contains photos of Che: his childhood in Argentina, his travels through South America, his involvement with the guerrillas in Cuba, Congo, and Bolivia, as well as personal items of the hero, such as documents, beret, pipe, clothing, weapons, rifle, asthma inhaler, and the saddle from the donkey that carried him through the jungles of Bolivia, along with copies of letters and his diary. The mausoleum holds the remains of Che Guevara and 38 of his companions who fought alongside him and died with him in Bolivia, fighting for a more just world, in 1966 and 1967. Dr. Ernesto Guevara, known to many simply as Che, was born in Argentina and had deep compassion for the suffering of the poor throughout Latin America. He was a Marxist revolutionary, doctor, guerrilla fighter, diplomat, and military theorist. He fought for the liberation of Cuba from a criminal and corrupt government, and for this reason, he is loved by everyone on the Island (**Photos 63-70**).

We left Santa Clara and headed to Trinidad, crossing the Sierra del Escambray. It was a two-hour journey through dense tropical forest (**Photo 71**). We stayed in a private house converted into a guesthouse. These private homes are excellent options for tourists throughout the Island. Trinidad was founded by Diego Velázquez in 1514 and was declared a World Heritage Site by UNESCO.

Diego Velázquez (1465-1524) was a Spanish conquistador who conquered Cuba with iron and fire in 1511, becoming the first governor of the Island. He sponsored expeditions of conquest on the American mainland, notably the one led by Hernán Cortés (1485-1547), which overthrew the Aztec civilization of Mexico. Velázquez and the Spanish encountered resistance in Cuba from the Taíno indigenous people, led by Hatuey. However, the Taíno were defeated and decimated in the following decades in a planned genocide. Using mastiff dogs and torturing the native people for information, the Spanish managed to capture Hatuey. On February 2, 1512, the indigenous leader was tied to a stake and burned alive in Yara, near the town of Bayamo. Before he was burned, a Franciscan friar asked Hatuey if he would accept Jesus, and then go to heaven. Hatuey, thinking for a moment, asked the friar if the Spaniards went to heaven. The friar answered yes. Hatuey then replied that he did not want to go to heaven but to hell, so he

would not meet the Spanish, such cruel people. Hatuey is considered Cuba's First National Hero [16].

Many similarities exist between Che Guevara and Hatuey. Neither was born in Cuba: Che Guevara was Argentine, born in the city of Rosario on June 14, 1928, while Hatuey was born on Hispaniola Island, in the province of Guahaba, possibly in present-day La Gonave, Haiti, in 1478. Both fought in Cuba for an ideal: freeing the Cuban people from oppressive foreign rule—Che Guevara against the North American empire and Hatuey against the Spanish empire. Both died far from their homeland: Che Guevara in Bolivia and Hatuey in Cuba, and both were cowardly murdered, each tied up in their final moments. Che was executed at the age of 39 by a rifle volley, while Hatuey was burned alive at the age of 34.

Trinidad is the third oldest city in Cuba (the first is Baracoa and the second is Bayamo). It boasts colonial architectural heritage from the 18th and 19th centuries, with cobblestone streets, churches, and restored buildings. Trinidad reached its peak during the sugar production era in the "Valle de los Ingenios," which is also a UNESCO World Heritage site and is worth a visit. The composition of the houses is like a beautiful painting, featuring pastel colors, some with tiled roofs, window grilles, and balusters designed by unique craftsmen (**Photos 72-92**).

The Plaza Mayor, located in the historic center of Trinidad, has been a prominent feature since the city's founding in 1514. Among the vibrant colors of the colonial buildings, yellow stands out, such as in the Casa de Aldemán Ortiz (**Photo 75**), which houses an art gallery, and the Museo de Arqueología Guamuhaya (**Photo 74**), where the naturalist Alexander von Humboldt (1769-1859) stayed in 1804. In the center of the square, you can admire the elegant mansions that surround it, along with the towering imperial palm trees (**Photos 72-76**).

We visited the Municipal Museum of Trinidad, popularly known as Palacio Cantero (**Photo 90**), where you can learn about the history of Trinidad, from its founding through the slave trade to the splendor of the sugar industry, with documents, works of art, and countless objects. One of the museum's main attractions is the breathtaking view of the city from the top of the tower (**Photos 87, 88**). After leaving Trinidad, we passed by the Mirador de La Loma del Puerto, where we enjoyed an incredible view of the "Valle de los Ingenios." The valley is a mosaic of vast sugarcane fields and green areas of properties and mills built in the early 18th century, with many imperial palm trees (**Photos 93, 94**).

The "Valle de los Ingenios" preserves 73 industrial archaeological sites as examples of the development of the sugar industry in the past, closely linked to the exploitation of slave labor. Throughout the 19th century, Havana was one of the largest slave cities in the New World [17]. Thousands of people were kidnapped from the African continent and forcibly brought to Cuba to work as slaves on sugar mills. In 1868, Cuba was responsible for 40% of the world's sugar production. Cuba was one of the last countries in the Americas to abolish slavery, on October 7, 1886. *La Última Cena* (The Last Supper) is a Cuban film directed by Tomás Gutiérrez Alea in 1976, a work against servitude that symbolizes the priceless value of freedom as an expression of human dignity.

The term "Afro-Cuban" refers to Cubans of African ancestry, as well as the historical, cultural, and intellectual elements that emanate from this community. A significant proportion of Cubans, around a third of the island's population, claim some African ancestry. Famous Afro-Cubans include Javier Sotomayor, holder of the World High Jump Record (he jumped 2.43m in 1993, a record that has not been broken to this day); singers Ibrahim Ferrer and Compay Segundo from the Buena Vista Social Club [18]; Juan Almeida, considered the third most influential figure in Cuban power after Fidel and Raul Castro; Harry Villegas (Pombo), a hero

of Cuba and communist guerrilla who fought alongside Che Guevara in the Cuban Revolution and in the guerrillas in Bolivia; Antonio Maceo, hero of the War of Independence; boxer Teófilo Stevenson, a three-time Olympic champion and three-time world champion; the greatest wrestler in history, Mijaín López, winner of five Olympic gold medals and five world championships in Greco-Roman wrestling. Mijaín López is the greatest Olympic champion in history, the only one to win five consecutive gold medals in the same individual category of the Olympic Games; Mireya Luis, a three-time Olympic champion and two-time world volleyball champion, considered by many critics to be the best volleyball player of all time; Pedro Luis Lazo, the greatest baseball champion in history; poet Nicolás Guillén; pianists Gonzalo Rubalcaba and Rubén González; and singers Pablo Milanés, Benny Moré, and Omara Portuondo.

Continuing our journey, we entered the city of Sancti Spíritus, crossing the terracotta arched bridge over the Yayabo River. Construction began in 1817, and it was officially opened in 1825. We drove through the narrow streets, lined with beautiful colonial houses restored and painted in pastel tones (**Photos 95, 96**). We then passed through Ciego de Ávila and dozens of small villages, where the people were very calm and friendly, always ready to offer information.

The virgin beaches and secluded privacy make tourism the only economic activity on the small islands surrounded by coral reefs, known as "cayos." These paradisiacal environments offer comfortable and modern hotel infrastructure, with luxurious all-inclusive resorts, among many facilities set in a natural environment in perfect harmony with the ecosystem (**Photos 101, 102**). Cayo Coco is one of these Caribbean paradises, located in the central region of Cuba, and is part of the island chain known as "Jardines del Rey" (King's Gardens). To reach this paradise, we had to cross a 30 km long artificial causeway (**Photo 97**), a road built over the sea, connecting the mainland to Cayo Coco. This island is also connected by a natural causeway to Cayo Guillermo and Cayo Romano (**Photos 105, 106**). There is also an airport on the island, which makes tourism more accessible. Cayo Coco is famous for its soft white sand beaches and coral reefs. The crystal-clear waters are an incredible turquoise blue (**Photos 98-100**). The surroundings are very calm, and between the beaches, there are shallow areas filled with flamingos, which makes the island even more charming (**Photos 103, 104**).

We headed towards the eastern part of Cuba, passing through the city of Ciego de Ávila, a modern city, and then Camagüey, an incredibly beautiful city declared a World Heritage Site by UNESCO (**Photos 107-113**). Founded in 1514 as Santa María del Puerto del Príncipe, Camagüey is the hometown of Nicolás Guillén (1902-1989), considered Cuba's national poet. The communist militant Guillén was, along with José Martí, known as "The Cuban Poet" par excellence [19]. Many of his poems were set to music by artists such as Quilapayún, Paco Ibáñez, Inti Illimani, and Xulio Formoso, who recorded an album entirely dedicated to his work in 1975, titled "Guillén el del son entero." Camagüey is also the birthplace of Ignacio Agramonte (1841-1873), an abolitionist lawyer and hero of Cuba's war of independence against Spain. Due to his battle skills, he was called "The Young Bolívar." Dr. Carlos Juan Finlay (1833-1915), the epidemiologist and scientist, was also born in Camagüey. In 1881, he discovered that yellow fever is transmitted from infected to healthy humans by a mosquito, identifying the genus *Aedes* as the transmitting agent.

Walking through Camagüey, we discovered several studios of the city's talented artists, including painters, artisans, musicians, and poets. In addition to its cultural repertoire, Camagüey boasts architectural elements and traditions that are authentic and exceptional, making the city rich in unique treasures. Camagüey is known as the "Ciudad de los Tinajones"

(City of the Large Jars). Tinajones are large containers that were used to store grains, oils, flour, and fresh water for human consumption. Skilled potters began making tinajones in the 17th century, using red clay from the Sierra de Cubitas. Some tinajones can still be seen around the city, decorating squares and gardens (**Photo 114**).

On the way to Bayamo, we passed through extensive areas of sugar cane plantations, valleys with imperial palm trees, and small towns like Guáimaro (**Photo 115**), located between the cities of Camagüey and Las Tunas (**Photo 116**). Guáimaro holds a prominent place in Cuban history as the site where, in 1869, at the beginning of the "Guerra de los Diez Años" (Ten Years' War, 1868-1878), the Revolutionary Army of the Mambises created the Guáimaro Constitution, which challenged Spanish colonial rule in Cuba [20]. This was the first of three conflicts aimed at Cuban secession from the Spanish Empire, followed by the Little War (1879-1880) and the Cuban War of Independence (1895-1898).

The Revolutionary Army of the Mambises was composed of Cubans from all social classes, including free blacks, mestizos, slaves, and landowners such as Carlos Manuel de Céspedes (1819-1874), known as the "Father of the Cuban Nation," all united by a common desire for freedom and independence for Cuba. The Mambí troops also included foreign officers and soldiers, such as the Polish Karol Rolow-Miałowski (1842-1907), better known as Carlos Roloff. In 1901, he was granted Cuban citizenship and appointed state treasurer of the independent republic, a position he held until his death [21]. The term "Mambises" is generally associated with Juan Ethnnius Mamby, known as Eutimio Mambí, a black officer who deserted the Spanish army and led the fight against the Spanish in Saint-Domingue (Haiti) 50 years before the first Cuban war of independence.

On October 20, 1868, Cuban revolutionary forces managed to liberate the city of Bayamo from Spanish rule. Patriot Perucho Figueredo composed the music for the anthem of free Cuba, "La Bayamesa," which would later officially become Cuba's national anthem. Figueredo was captured and executed by the Spanish two years later, but before the firing squad executed him, he shouted the line from his song: "Morir por la Patria es vivir" (to die for the homeland is to live).

Bayamo is a very pleasant city, not only for its rich colonial architecture but also for its people, which can be observed by strolling through Parque Céspedes at night. There, we can see young and old people talking, children playing, all in perfect harmony, in an almost complete silence that respects the existence of this beautiful and historic city. Parque Céspedes is one of Cuba's leafiest squares. Bayamo's central meeting point is surrounded by pedestrian-only streets, making it a peaceful spot. Bayamo is the second oldest city in Cuba, founded by Diego Velázquez in 1513. The historic center is beautiful, with renovated buildings painted in the original pastel colors (**Photos 117-127**). It is the city of Carlos Manuel de Céspedes, a lawyer who became a hero when he commanded an army in 1868 to free the city from Spanish oppression.

We continued to the Sierra Maestra and made a stop in Yara (**Photos 128-130**), the city of the revolutionary Bartolomé Masó (1830-1907), President of the Republic of Cuba in Arms between 1897 and 1899. It is also the hometown of Harry Villegas, better known by his nickname "Pombo" (1940-2019), a communist guerrilla and descendant of African slaves who fought alongside Che Guevara in battles from the Sierra Maestra to the guerrillas in Bolivia, being one of the few survivors. Yara is the city where the indigenous leader Hatuey was burned at the stake by the Spanish invaders on February 2, 1512, and it was in this city that Céspedes proclaimed the Cuban Republic on October 10, 1868, giving the "Grito de Yara," declaring

Cuba's independence and starting the Ten Years' War: "That morning, after hearing the slaves' bell, which signaled to them that it was time for work, Céspedes announced that they were all free men and invited them to join him and his companions in the conspiracy for war against the Spanish government in Cuba. That is why he is called 'Padre de la Patria' (Father of the Homeland). In April 1869, he was chosen president of the Republic of Cuba in Arms".

We considered crossing the Sierra Maestra to the coast, as the route is shorter, but some people in Yara advised us not to venture into the Sierra because our car did not have four-wheel drive. We decided to go around Manzanillo, a longer but safer route. We stopped for coffee and toured Manzanillo and Media Luna, two very beautiful and well-organized cities. In Media Luna, we visited the house where Célia Sánchez lived (**Photos 131-133**), a Cuban heroine who organized a rear guard in this small town when Fidel and the guerrillas disembarked, a few kilometers from here, at Playa Las Coloradas, with the Granma yacht, on December 2, 1956. The Granma (slang for grandmother), 18 meters long, was powered by diesel and was built in 1943, designed to accommodate 12 people. However, Fidel Castro managed to fit he and 81 other revolutionaries, who left Mexico—where Fidel was in exile and where he met Dr. Che Guevara—until landing on a Cuban beach to carry out the Cuban Revolution. This vessel has historical significance, as the landing of Fidel Castro and his companions marked the birth of the Rebel Army, which was the decisive protagonist of the war that followed, leading to Fidel Castro and the communists coming to power.

The Sierra Maestra (**Photo 134**) is a mountain range located in the southeastern region of Cuba, with Pico Turquino being the highest point, at around 2,000 meters. This mountain range, which had already played a significant role in three wars of independence against Spain in the 19th century, would once again play a pivotal role in libertarian history during the revolutionary war of communist guerrillas against the dictator Fulgencio Batista.

Why Sierra Maestra? The mountain range is considered the birthplace of guerrilla warfare par excellence. Initially, this is due to the presence of dense forests, which allow the guerrillas to hide, set up ambushes, and escape persecution—essentially, for tactical reasons. The guerrillas also need supplies and must maintain contact with the cities and even the outside world. There are two types of guerrillas: those in which the guerrillas are locals, who know the mountains and forests well, while the army is hindered by its poor knowledge of the terrain; and those led by men who are not from the region, who know less about the place than the soldiers who pursue them. This was the case of the guerrillas in the Sierra Maestra and in Bolivia. Therefore, one of the essential conditions for the guerrillas' survival is that they are informed, guided, and supported by the local population. In most of the guerrilla movements that emerged in Latin America, support was very weak, and sometimes the population was hostile, as was the case of Che in Bolivia. The Sierra Maestra guerrillas were an exception. Fidel and his companions, who disembarked from Granma, almost completely ignored the mountain range where they would have to fight. They didn't even have maps of the Sierra. So why did Fidel choose the Sierra Maestra? Fidel's first attempt was in the famous attack on the Moncada Barracks in Santiago, on July 26, 1953. The repression following this attack was widespread, with numerous murders of rebels and civilians. Frank País (1934-1957), a Cuban intellectual and revolutionary from Santiago, was supposed to play a crucial role when the Granma landed, triggering an insurrection in eastern Cuba's capital. Another issue was the almost 800 kilometers that separated Havana from the East. Therefore, the guerrillas, both from Santiago and those disembarking from Granma, might have had some time before the arrival

of Batista's forces. On the way between Media Luna and Pílon, on the coast, billboards indicated that Che and the guerrillas had passed through there in December 1956 (**Photos 135-138**).

We had lunch at Marea del Portillo, a beautiful beach (**Photo 139**). We had the entire afternoon to travel about 180 km to Santiago de Cuba, and we thought it wouldn't be that difficult, but it turned out to be almost a nightmare, as the road had been partially destroyed by Hurricane Sandy, which passed through Cuba on October 25, a week before our trip. The hurricane had devastated everything in its path. The south coast is truly magnificent, with an indescribably intense turquoise-blue sea. The Sierra Maestra frames the landscape, coming very close to the sea in some places (**Photos 140-144**). Many specimens of purple sea fan (*Gorgonia ventalina*) [22] were on the seabed, brought there by the hurricane. In the end, we arrived in Santiago de Cuba at night.

Perched above a bay in the Caribbean Sea, with views of the Sierra Maestra, Santiago de Cuba, founded by the Spanish in 1515, is known for its colonial architecture and revolutionary history. At the entrance to the city, billboards indicate that the communist revolution defeated the North American parasites, and that this is the hometown of communist revolutionary Frank País (1934-1957). País was the urban coordinator of the 26th of July Movement and a key organizer within the urban underground movement, collaborating with Fidel Castro's guerrilla forces, which were conducting activities in the Sierra Maestra mountains. País was murdered in the streets of Santiago de Cuba by the Santiago police on July 30, 1957. According to some historians, País was the main organizer of the Cuban revolution, and according to Fidel, he was the most extraordinary of the combatants. Antonio Maceo Revolution Square covers 53 thousand square meters and features the tallest statue in Cuba, a 16-meter-high monument to Antonio Maceo (1845-1896), accompanied by 23 stylized machetes representing March 23, 1878, when the revolution for Cuban independence resumed (**Photos 145-148**).

In a village near Santiago de Cuba, Antonio Maceo, a hero of the War of Independence, was born. He was nicknamed "El Titán de Bronce" (Bronze Titan), a reference to his skin tone and physical strength. The Spanish called him "El León Mayor" (Greater Lion). Maceo was one of the most notable guerrilla leaders in 19th-century Latin America. He participated in more than 500 battles. The use of the machete as a weapon of war by General Máximo Gómez (1836-1905) as a substitute for the Spanish sword, due to the scarcity of firearms and ammunition, was quickly adopted by Maceo and his troops. Maceo fought in the Ten Years' War and the Cuban War of Independence, alongside José Martí. Foreseeing the rise of American expansionism and the United States' desire to annex Cuba and make it "another star in the constellation of the United States," he was strongly opposed to the acceptance of direct US military intervention in Cuba. In addition to his role as a soldier and statesman in the Cuban independence movement, Maceo was an influential political strategist and military planner. Maceo died in battle, along with Francisco Gómez, the son of Máximo Gómez, before seeing Cuba's independence.

We visited Ciudad Escolar 26 de Julio (26th of July School City), the former Cuartel Moncada (Moncada Barracks). The Cuban Revolution officially began on July 26, 1953, when young lawyer Fidel Castro and around 100 rebels attempted to take over the barracks. Unfortunately, the attack on the barracks and other strategic locations in the city was unsuccessful. Eight rebels were killed in the attack, and 55 were arrested, tortured, and executed on the same day, including Abel Santamaría. Abel Santamaría (1927-1953) was a Cuban revolutionary activist who actively participated in the assault on Cuartel Moncada, where he was captured, savagely tortured, and murdered. He was the brother of Haydée, a revolutionary

who was always by his side, including during the assault on the barracks. Cuban composer and singer Silvio Rodríguez composed "Canción del Elegido" for this great Cuban hero in 1968. The brothers Fidel and Raúl were arrested, tried, and sentenced to 15 years in prison. Fidel delivered his self-defense speech before the court, which would later be known as "History Will Absolve Me". He was freed through an amnesty in 1955 and went into exile in Mexico, where he met Che Guevara and organized his return to Cuba on December 2, 1956, marking the beginning of the guerrilla war. Currently, Abel Santamaria's ashes rest in a monument at the Santa Ifigênia Cemetery in Santiago de Cuba, near Fidel Castro's tomb.

Some bullet marks from that July 26th are still visible on the wall at the entrance to the old barracks. Currently, Ciudad Escolar 26 de Julio (**Photos 149-151**) has the capacity to accommodate approximately 2,000 students, who receive free, high-quality education, as guaranteed by Cuba's communist constitution. The school is equipped with educational materials, 80 classrooms, and even a medical center, as well as a history museum that tells the story of the building.

Hurricane Sandy passed through Santiago de Cuba between October 25th and 26th, from 11 pm to 5 am, and we were able to see the damage it caused to the city, knocking down trees and damaging houses. We visited the Castillo de San Pedro de la Roca del Morro, or simply Castillo del Morro, a military fortress declared a World Heritage Site by UNESCO. This Renaissance military fortification was built in 1638 with the aim of protecting the city of Santiago de Cuba from a naval attack. On July 3, 1898, the fortification played a key role in one of the most important events in American history: the Naval Battle of Santiago de Cuba, an event that marked the end of Spanish rule on the continent. It is considered by experts to be the largest and most complete example of military construction from the Spanish Renaissance in the New World [23]. We took a detailed tour of all the rooms, artillery areas, and casemates of this 17th-century fortress. We also enjoyed various views of the beautiful Santiago Bay and the Sierra Maestra (**Photos 152-156**).

We visited Diego Velázquez's house, probably the oldest residence in Cuba, built in 1522 to house Cuba's first governor. It was restored in 1965 and transformed into the Museum of Historical Cuban Atmosphere, with furniture from the 16th to the 19th centuries. This National Monument preserves pieces of French, English, Spanish, and Cuban origin, including valuable porcelain. There is also a furnace where, in colonial times, gold was smelted. The museum offers a journey through time, showcasing Cuban furniture. The courtyard is beautiful, in the Mudéjar style, with elegant wooden railings. The frescoes that decorate the internal walls were restored from the originals dating back to the early 16th century. The ceilings are made of cedar, and the furniture is of high luxury, featuring pieces of Meissen porcelain, Venetian chandeliers, Bohemian crystal, stained glass, and French furniture (**Photos 159-163**). After this wonderful visit, we enjoyed a first-rate musical performance in the museum's courtyard, featuring traditional Cuban music: clarinet, tuba, cello, percussion, trumpet, and voice, along with the traditional güiro, a percussion instrument often used as an accompaniment in typical Caribbean music rhythms (**Photos 164-166**). The Cuban güiro is made from a gourd with parallel grooves on its surface. It is held with one hand, while the other is used to scrape the surface with a stick.

In the museum square, there are two other tourist attractions: the "Ayuntamiento" (**Photo 157**), which is the city hall of Santiago de Cuba, a 16th-century building constructed by Diego Velázquez, who appointed Hernán Cortés as the city's first mayor. From the central balcony of this building, Fidel Castro proclaimed the triumph of the Cuban Revolution on January 1, 1959. Over the years, Fidel's speeches were often given from this location. The other attraction is the

Catedral de Nuestra Señora de la Asunción, the first church in Santiago de Cuba, built in 1514 (**Photo 158**). Diego Velázquez was buried in this church, but to this day, the exact location of his grave remains unknown.

This historic region of Santiago de Cuba deserves a very detailed visit, as you walk through the narrow streets, where historical monuments and wonderful views come to light (**Photos 167, 168**). The Museo Municipal Emilio Bacardi Moreau (Emilio Bacardi Moreau Municipal Museum) has an impressive Greek-style facade with Corinthian columns (**Photo 169**) and displays a varied and intriguing collection of objects collected during the Bacardis' travels around the world. Emilio Bacardi Moreau (1844-1922) was a Cuban industrialist, politician, and writer who managed the Bacardi Rum Company.

The Museo de la Lucha Clandestina (Museum of Clandestine Struggle) (**Photo 170**) tells a lesser-known part of the Revolution, focusing on the strategy and organization of the revolutionary movement. A visit to this beautiful museum offers an opportunity to learn about the actions that freed Cuba from a bloodthirsty dictator. The Balcón Velázquez is a stunning viewpoint offering a beautiful view of Santiago Bay (**Photo 171**). Climbing the Padre Pico staircase, which leads to the Tívoli neighborhood (**Photos 172-174**), we pass by the Museo de la Lucha Clandestina and the house where young Fidel lived with his family. We visited the Casa de las Tradiciones (House of Traditions), where the first filming of *Buena Vista Social Club* took place. We continued our tour along the streets of Santiago, such as Calle Heredia and Calle Aguillera, which are the two busiest in the historic center. We finished our tour with coffee at the traditional and historic La Isabelica.

CONCLUSIONS

Cuba is one of the most beautiful countries we have ever visited, and we recommend it to anyone looking for a safe and pleasant trip, rich in culture and natural beauty. It is the country where we feel safest, as this Caribbean island embodies the peace we desire, with freedom and love visible everywhere we went. We believe there is no country more loved than Cuba, not only in the verses of José Martí and Silvio Rodríguez but also in the eyes of Cubans, who have a true love for their country. It seems they will never forget Che, Fidel, Raul, Camilo, Célia, Haydée, Abel, Frank, and others who fought so that Cuba could become a free and sovereign nation.

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Appendix

Photo 1. The Castillo del Morro is an example of 16th-century architecture in Havana, Cuba. It is a colonial fortress built by the Spanish Empire.

Photo 2. The Malecón is a wide esplanade, roadway, and seawall that stretches for 8 km along the coast of Havana.

Photo 3. Havana's cathedral, built in the 18th century, is the best example of Cuban Baroque architecture.

Photo 4. The Palacio del Marqués de Arcos is one of the gems of Cuban Baroque and one of the most important examples of 18th-century residential architecture.

Photo 5. The Palacio de los Capitanes Generales is considered the most important architectural work of the entire Baroque era in Cuba.

Photo 6. Architectural detail of Old Havana (Habana Vieja).

Photo 7. Architectural detail of Old Havana (Habana Vieja).

Photo 8. Detail of the architecture of Old Havana with Art Nouveau-style stained glass windows.

Photo 9. Architectural detail of Old Havana (Habana Vieja).

Photo 10. Architectural detail of Old Havana (Habana Vieja).

Photo 11. Detail for the Habana Libre, which was the Habana Hilton Hotel before the Cuban Revolution.

Photo 12. Edificio Focsa, built in 1956, is based on Le Corbusier's ideas of an autonomous city within a city.

Photo 13. The design of the National Capitol in Havana is similar to the United States Capitol in Washington, D.C., but its dome is inspired by the dome of the Pantheon in Paris.

Photo 14. The Grand Theater of Havana Alicia Alonso (Gran Teatro de La Habana).

Photo 15. Architectural detail of Old Havana (Habana Vieja).

Photo 16. Architectural detail of old Havana (Habana Vieja).

Photo 17. Detail of vintage cars on the streets of Havana, Cuba.

Photo 18. Detail of vintage cars on the streets of Havana, Cuba.

Photo 19. Detail of vintage cars on the streets of Havana, Cuba.

Photo 20. Detail of vintage cars on the streets of Havana, Cuba.

Photo 21. Museum of the Revolution, Havana, Cuba.

Photo 22. With this 100 mm caliber cannon, Commander Fidel Castro fired at the US vessel *Houston* during the mercenary invasion of Playa Girón in April 1961.

Photo 23. Statues of Che Guevara, Fidel Castro, and Camilo Cienfuegos at the Museum of the Revolution in Havana.

Photo 24. Detail of the wax statue of Che Guevara, one of the heroes of the Cuban Revolution.

Photo 25. The vehicle used by Fidel Castro in the failed attempt to take the Moncada Barracks in Santiago de Cuba on July 26, 1953. Detail of the gunshot marks on the bodywork.

Photo 26. The Cretins panel, from left to right: Batista, Ronald Reagan, George Bush father and son. The first was a US puppet, while the last three, former Presidents of the United States, were responsible for various terrorist actions against Cuba and the Cuban people.

Photo 27. The Cuban flag at the Museum of the Revolution.

Photo 28. View through a window of the Museum of the Revolution.

Photo 29. In Cuba, a "paladar" is a small family-run restaurant. It offers a great opportunity to enjoy homemade Cuban cuisine.

Photo 30. Tricycles with a double seat behind the cyclist travel around Habana Vieja, transporting tourists between points of interest.

Photo 31. The "cocotaxi" is a motorized tricycle resembling a scooter, with a double or triple seat behind the driver, covered by a spherical structure open at the front.

Photo 32. This is another type of motorized tricycle used as a taxi.

Photo 33. Real Fabrika de Tabacos Partagás, where the famous Montecristo and Cohíba cigars are handcrafted.

Photo 34. Calle Obispo, the busiest street in Old Havana (Habana Vieja).

Photo 35. Calle Obispo, featuring the Hotel Ambos Mundos in pink, where writer Ernest Hemingway lived between 1932 and 1939 and wrote the novel *For Whom the Bell Tolls*.

Photo 36. The Mural Painting Museum (Museo de los Murales) is located in a historic building, considered the oldest house in Havana.

Photo 37. The Coppelita ice cream parlor was designed to serve a thousand people at the same time, featuring a hall and an ice cream factory.

Photo 38. Coppelita is a reference in ice cream production worldwide.

Photo 39. Casa de las Américas is an organization founded in Cuba in 1959 to promote the exchange of Cuban culture with that of other Latin American countries.

Photo 40. La Plaza de la Revolución is one of the largest squares in the world. The building on the left, with the enormous mural of Che Guevara is the Ministry of the Interior. The building on the right, with the image of Camilo Cienfuegos, is the Ministry of Telecommunications.

Photo 41. In the center of Plaza de la Revolución is the José Martí Memorial, a 142-meter-high monument, the tallest structure in all of Havana...

Photo 42. ... and just in front of the monument, there is a 17-meter-high marble statue representing José Martí, seated and pensive.

Photo 43. Varadero, one of the most sought-after destinations in the Caribbean.

Photo 44. The luxurious Mansion Xanadu Hotel, formerly the beach house of French-American millionaire Irénée Dupont, in Varadero.

Photo 45. Detail of the incredible geological formation called mogotes, in the Viñales Valley, in Pinar del Río, in the western part of Cuba.

Photo 46. The mogotes are one of the reasons why the Viñales Valley was declared a World Heritage Site by UNESCO.

Photo 47. Detail of a tobacco barn, used for drying and curing tobacco leaves. Doors and windows can be opened to control temperature and humidity.

Photo 48. Rural workers in the Pinar del Río region, who grow tobacco, are called guajiros.

Photo 49. On the surface of a mogote in the Valle de Las Dos Hermanas, one can find one of the most well-known attractions: the Mural de la Prehistoria, by muralist Leovigildo González.

Photo 50. Starting from Havana, after a two-hour taxi ride or a bus excursion organized by travel agencies located in the city's main hotels, you will arrive in the Viñales Valley.

Photo 51. Continuing by car towards Cienfuegos, we pass through a large area of sugarcane plantations.

Photo 52. Detail of the Catedral de la Purísima Concepción, built in 1869 in neoclassical style, Cienfuegos, Cuba.

Photo 53. The Tomás Terry Theater, declared a national monument, is considered one of the most elegant eclectic buildings in Cienfuegos. The legendary Italian tenor Enrico Caruso performed at this theater in the early 1920s.

Photo 54. Museo de las Artes Palacio Ferrer, Cienfuegos, Cuba.

Photo 55. We stayed at the Palacio Azul hotel, a beautiful pastel-blue mansion from 1921, facing the stunning bay of Cienfuegos.

Photo 56. Another accommodation option in Cienfuegos, also located on the seafont.

Photo 57. A statue of singer Benny Moré on a sidewalk in Cienfuegos.

Photo 58. Cienfuegos, Cuba.

Photo 59. Detail of classic facades and columns reminiscent of 19th-century France. Cienfuegos, Cuba.

Photo 60. The Palacio de Valle de Cienfuegos, built in 1917 by the Asturian Acisclo Valle Blanco is shaped like an excessively ornate Moroccan casbah.

Photo 61. A billboard on the road to Santa Clara features the flags of Cuba and Venezuela, with the faces of José Martí and Simón Bolívar, calling for a just world order.

Photo 62. Another billboard on the same road displays a photo of Che Guevara and the words: 'It was a star that put you here and made you of this town.'

Photo 63. A billboard with the words: 'Thank you, Che, for your story, your life, and your example!' Che Guevara Mausoleum in Santa Clara, Cuba.

Photo 64. A Cuban flag in front of Che Guevara's Mausoleum in Santa Clara, Cuba.

Photo 65. ¡Hasta la victoria siempre! (Until victory always!) Statue of Che Guevara in front of the Che Guevara Mausoleum in Sana Clara, Cuba.

Photo 66. Photograph of Che Guevara taken by Cuban photographer Alberto "Korda" Gutierrez (1928-2001) on March 5, 1960 in Cuba, titled *Guerrillero Heroico* (Heroic Guerrilla).

Photo 67. Fidel Castro and his men in the Sierra Maestra. From left: Guillermo García, Che Guevara, Universo Sánchez, Raúl Castro (kneeling), Fidel, Crescencio Pérez, Jorge Sotus, and Juan Almeida. This work was created in Cuba on 2 December 1956, by an unknown author and is now in the public domain.

Photo 68. Armored Train Monument, derailed by Che Guevara during the capture of Santa Clara.

Photo 69. Santa Clara, Cuba.

Photo 70. Santa Clara, Cuba.

Photo 71. Before arriving in Trinidad, we cross the Sierra del Escambray, passing through dense tropical forests.

Photo 72. The Plaza Mayor, located in the historic center of Trinidad, has been there since the city's founding in 1514.

Photo 73. In the center of the square, you can see the elegant mansions that surround it, along with the imperial palm trees. Trinidad, Cuba.

Photo 74. Museo de Arqueología Guamuhaya, where the naturalist Alexander von Humboldt stayed in 1804. Trinidad, Cuba.

Photo 75. Among the bright colors of the colonial buildings, yellow stands out, such as in the Casa de Aldemán Ortiz, where an art gallery operates. Trinidad, Cuba.

Photo 76. The Casa de los Conspiradores (House of Conspirators), in Trinidad, Cuba, features a charming corner balcony with a turned wooden balustrade that serves as a parapet.

Photo 77. The composition of the houses is like a beautiful painting, with pastel colors. Trinidad, Cuba.

Photo 78. Trinidad boasts colonial architectural heritage from the 18th and 19th centuries, featuring stone-lined streets, churches, and restored buildings.

Photo 79. Antique cars are also present in Trinidad.

Photo 80. A detail of an old car on a street in Trinidad.

Photo 81. Trinidad, Cuba.

Photo 82. All Cuban children attend public schools of excellent quality and take pride in their country.

Photo 83. Trinidad, Cuba: colonial house with traditional wooden beams (window grille)...

Photo 84. ... window grilles from unique designers.

Photo 85. Trinidad, considered a UNESCO World Heritage site, is one of the most beautiful cities in Cuba.

Photo 86. Trinidad, Cuba.

Photo 87. A view of the city from the top of the tower of the Palacio Cantero, with the Sierra del Escambray in the background.

Photo 88. Trinidad, considered a UNESCO World Heritage site, is one of the most beautiful cities in Cuba.

Photo 89. Detail of a variety store in Trinidad, Cuba.

Photo 90. Detail of the entrance hall of the Municipal Museum of Trinidad, commonly known as Palacio Cantero.

Photo 91. Trinidad, Cuba.

Photo 92. Trinidad, Cuba.

Photo 93. Trinidad had its heyday with sugar production in the “Valle de los Ingenios”, which is also considered a UNESCO World Heritage site. A detail of the Sierra del Escambray is visible in the background...

Photo 94. ... the valley is formed by a mosaic of extensive sugarcane plantations and green areas of properties and mills built in the early 18th century, with many imperial palm trees.

Photo 95. Sancti Spiritus, a city with narrow streets with beautiful colonial houses that have been restored and painted in pastel tones.

Photo 96. Historic center of Sancti Spiritus, Cuba.

Photo 97. To reach Cayo Coco, we had to cross a 30 km-long artificial causeway that connects the mainland to the island.

Photo 98. Cayo Coco is one of the Caribbean's paradises, located in the central region of Cuba, and is part of the chain of islands known as “Jardines del Rey.”

Photo 99. Cayo Coco is famous for its soft, white sand beaches and coral reefs...

Photo 100. ... and the crystal-clear waters are an incredible shade of turquoise blue.

Photo 101. *Melanerpes superciliaris* (known in Cuba as carpintero jabado) is the most common of the woodpecker in Cuba. It inhabits forests with scattered trees and can also be found in gardens and parks in cities.

Photo 102. The Greater Antilles grackle (*Quiscalus niger*) is a gregarious bird common in Cuba that frequents anthropogenic environments.

Photo 103. The Caribbean flamingo (*Phoenicopterus ruber*) is a gregarious bird that lives and nests in large colonies ...

Photo 104. ... It frequents saltwater lagoons and freshwater habitats, including mudflats, estuaries, and inland and coastal lakes.

Photo 105. A lighthouse located on Cayo Romano.

Photo 106. Cayo Romano, Cuba.

Photo 107. Camagüey is an incredibly beautiful city that has been declared a UNESCO World Heritage Site.

Photo 108. Founded in 1514 as Santa María del Puerto del Príncipe, Camagüey is the hometown of Nicolás Guillén (1902-1989), who is considered Cuba's national poet.

Photo 109. Camagüey, Cuba.

Photo 110. Camagüey, Cuba: The City of Artists.

Photo 111. Camagüey, Cuba.

Photo 112. Camagüey, Cuba.

Photo 113. Camagüey, Cuba.

Photo 114. Camagüey is known as the “Ciudad de los Tinajones”, referring to large containers made of red clay that were traditionally used to store grains, oils, flour, and fresh water for human consumption.

Photo 115. A billboard on the road between the cities of Camagüey and Las Tunas reads: “Guáimaro, the Republic of Cuba was born here”, referencing the site of Cuba's first revolutionary constitution, which challenged Spanish colonial rule in Cuba.

Photo 116. A billboard on the road reads: “Welcome to Las Tunas, the Balcony of Eastern Cuba.”

Photo 117. Bayamo is the second oldest city in Cuba, founded by Diego Velázquez in 1513.

Photo 118. The historic center of Bayamo is beautiful, featuring renovated buildings painted in their original pastel tones.

Photo 119. Bayamo public library, built in 1868, the year the “Guerra de los Diez Años” (Ten Years' War) began.

Photo 120. Bayamo, Cuba.

Photo 121. The house of Carlos Manuel de Céspedes in Bayamo, Cuba.

Photo 122. Parque Céspedes is one of Cuba's leafiest squares and serves as Bayamo's central meeting place.

Photo 123. Bayamo is a very pleasant city, not only for its rich colonial architecture...

Photo 124. ... but also for its people.

Photo 125. Historic center of Bayamo, Cuba.

Photo 126. A detail of one of the squares in the historic center of Bayamo, Cuba.

Photo 127. Bayamo, Cuba.

Photo 128. Buey Arriba is a municipality and city in the Granma province of Cuba, located 30 kilometers south of Bayamo.

Photo 129. Along the roads in the province of Granma, there are billboards featuring drawings of revolutionary heroes from the region who died fighting in the Cuban Revolution (July 26, 1953 to January 1, 1959). A detail of the Sierra Maestra is visible in the background.

Photo 130. Billboards featuring drawings of revolutionary heroes who gave their lives for the Cuban Revolution (July 26, 1953 to January 1, 1959).

Photo 131. Celia Sánchez's house in Media Luna, Cuba.

Photo 132. A tree-lined square in Media Luna, Cuba.

Photo 133. A well-preserved vintage car in Media Luna, Cuba.

Photo 134. Tropical forest in the Sierra Maestra, Cuba.

Photo 135. A billboard in the Sierra Maestra indicating that Che Guevara and the guerrillas passed through the area on December 19, 1956.

Photo 136. A billboard in the Sierra Maestra indicating that Raul Castro and the guerrillas passed through the area on December 17, 1956.

Photo 137. Guerrillas Che Guevara and Fidel with companions in the Sierra Maestra.

Photo 138. The guerrillas Fidel Castro and Juan Almeida in the Sierra Maestra.

Photo 139. A detail of the beautiful Marea del Portillo beach, located 180 kilometers from Santiago.

Photo 140. The southeast coast of Cuba is truly wonderful, with an indescribably intense turquoise-blue sea.

Photo 141. Coast of Cuba, between Marea del Portillo and Santiago.

Photo 142. Beautiful landscapes along the coast of Cuba, between Marea del Portillo and Santiago.

Photo 143. The road between Marea del Portillo and Santiago was partially destroyed by Hurricane Isaac at the end of August 2012.

Photo 144. The Sierra Maestra frames the landscape, coming very close to the sea in some areas.

Photo 145. A billboard at the entrance to Santiago de Cuba reads: “with everyone's effort, we will overcome”, the criminal economic embargo imposed by the United States in 1962.

Photo 146. The tallest statue in Cuba, standing 16 meters high, honors Antonio Maceo and is located in Santiago.

Photo 147. A billboard featuring a photo of Frank País and Fidel's words: "Frank was the most useful, the most extraordinary of our fighters".

Photo 148. A monument to Abel Santamaría in Santiago de Cuba.

Photo 149. Cuidad Escolar 26 de Julio, formerly Cuartel Moncada, Santiago de Cuba.

Photo 150. Some bullet marks from that July 26th are still visible on the wall at the entrance to the old barracks.

Photo 151. Ciudad Escolar 26 de Julio has capacity for approximately 2,000 students, who receive free, high-quality education, as guaranteed by Cuba's communist constitution.

Photo 152. Castillo de San Pedro de la Roca del Morro, or simply Castillo del Morro is a military fortress that has been declared a UNESCO World Heritage Site.

Photo 153. This Renaissance military fortification was built in 1638 with the aim of protecting the city of Santiago de Cuba from a naval attack.

Photo 154. Castillo del Morro is considered by experts to be the largest and most complete example of military architecture from the Spanish Renaissance in the New World.

Photo 155. A detail of the Santiago Bay and the Sierra Maestra seen from the Castillo del Morro.

Photo 156. A detail of the Santiago Bay and the Sierra Maestra seen from the Castillo del Morro.

Photo 157. Detail of the Ayuntamiento (City Hall) of Santiago de Cuba.

Photo 158. Catedral de Nuestra Señora de la Asunción, the first church in Santiago de Cuba, was built in 1514.

Photo 159. Diego Velázquez's house is probably the oldest residence in Cuba, built in 1522 to welcome Cuba's first governor.

Photo 160. Diego Velázquez's house was restored in 1965 and transformed into the Museum of Historical Cuban Atmosphere, featuring furniture from the 16th to the 19th centuries.

Photo 161. The Museum of Historical Cuban Atmosphere preserves pieces of French, English, Spanish and Cuban origin, including very valuable porcelain.

Photo 162. The Museum of Historical Cuban Atmosphere is a journey through time, showcasing Cuban furniture.

Photo 163. The museum is frequently visited by schools and organizes traditional Cuban music performances every Sunday at 10:30 a.m.

Photo 164. Cello, clarinet, and the traditional güiro, a percussion instrument that often used as accompaniment in typical Caribbean music rhythms.

Photo 165. Cello, and trumpet, in the presentation of traditional Cuban music.

Photo 166. The friendly guide who introduced us to the museum.

Photo 167. Vintage cars drive through the streets of Santiago de Cuba.

Photo 168. Vintage cars drive through the streets of Santiago de Cuba.

Photo 169. The impressive Greek-style facade of the Emilio Bacardi Moreau Municipal Museum, Santiago de Cuba.

Photo 170. The Museo de la Lucha Clandestina (Museum of Clandestine Struggle) tells the story of a lesser-known part of the Revolution.

Photo 171. Balcón Velázquez is a beautiful viewpoint that offers a stunning view of Santiago Bay.

Photo 172. The Padre Pico staircase leads to the Tívoli neighborhood.

Photo 173. Historic center of Santiago de Cuba.

Photo 174. Historic center of Santiago de Cuba.